

Competency Questions

Id CQ	Competency Questions description
CQ1	Which community smells are linked to the socio-technical factors that contribute to the emergence of social debt?
CQ2	Which causes, associated with a specific socio-technical factor, influence the emergence and management of social debt?
CQ3	Which socio-technical factors are impacted by social debt?
CQ4	What are the effects generated by a cause of social debt within the context of a specific socio-technical factor?
CQ5	Which corrective strategies address the specific effects of social debt according to the socio-technical factor they impact?
CQ6	Which preventive strategies address a specific cause of social debt according to the socio-technical factor it affects?
CQ7	Which community smells arise from the socio-technical factors and causes that contribute to social debt in a specific development team?
CQ8	Which negative effects does the presence of a specific community smell have on team members, the organization, or software quality?
CQ9	Which strategies help prevent or reduce the impact of a specific community smell that contributes to social debt accumulation?
CQ10	Which indicators can be used to identify a specific cause of social debt?
CQ11	Which metrics help measure how a specific cause impacts the team or the organization?

Acronyms used: Competency Questions (CQ).